

Synthesis and biological evaluation of 3-(phthalimidoethyl)-4-(5-substituted isoxazoline and pyrazoline) substituted benzanilides

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Abstract : 3-Phthalimidoethyl benzoic acids 2a-g were prepared by treating *N*-hydroxy-ethylphthalimide 1 with substituted benzoic acids. The corresponding acid chlorides 3a-g were condensed with 4-aminoacetophenone in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate to give 3-phthalimidoethyl-4-acetyl substituted benzanilides 4a-g. The substituted benzanilide derivatives 4a-g were condensed with diverse aromatic aldehydes to afford compounds 5a₁-d₇. Compounds 5a₁-7...d₁-7 on treatment with hydroxylamine hydrochloride and hydrazine dihydrochloride separately in the presence of sodium acetate afforded titled compounds 6a₁-7...d₁-7 and 7a₁-9. The structures of the newly synthesized compounds have been established by elemental analysis and spectral data and some of the selected compounds have been screened for their antibacterial, antifungal, anthelmintic and hypoglycemic activities.

Keywords : Phthalimide, isoxazole, pyrazole, antimicrobial, anthelmintic activity.

Introduction

The phthalimide derivatives have been reported to possess diverse biological activities^{1,2}, including anticancer, antitumor promoting agent, immunosuppressant, antiviral, hypoglycemic and antimicrobial activities. A number of biological activities like antibacterial, antifungal, antidiabetic and anti-inflammatory are associated with pyrazolines^{3,6} and isoxazolines⁷. Based on these observations and in continuation of our work on substituted phthalimido derivatives⁸, we report here synthesis (Scheme 1) of the title compounds and their biological evaluation.

The required starting material *N*-hydroxyethylphthalimide 1 was prepared by Mannich condensation of phthalic anhydride and 2-aminoethanol as per the reported method⁹. Compound 1 on condensation with various substituted benzoic acids in ethanol as solvent yielded 3-phthalimidoethyl substituted benzoic acids 2a-g^{1,8} which on treatment with thionyl chloride afforded corresponding acid chlorides 3a-g. Compounds 4a-g were prepared by refluxing acid chlorides 3a-g and 4-aminoacetophenone in carbon tetrachloride in the presence of anhydrous po-

tassium carbonate. The condensation of substituted benzanilide derivatives 4a-g with various arylaldehydes in ethanol resulted in the formation of 3-phthalimidoethyl-4-substituted cinammonyl substituted benzanilides 5a₁-d₇, which on treatment with hydroxylamine hydrochloride and hydrazine dihydrochloride separately in the presence of sodium acetate afforded the title compounds 6a₁-7...d₁-7 and 7a₁-9 respectively. The structure of these compounds was confirmed by spectral (IR, ¹H NMR, Mass) studies and elemental analysis.

Results and discussion

The CMC suspension of synthesized compounds were shown to produce reduction in the blood glucose concentration between 8 h of administration in two methods, normoglycemic rats¹⁰ and alloxan induced hyperglycemic rats¹¹ at a tested dose of 250 mg/kg of body weight. When compared with reference glyclazide administered at a dose of 2.5 mg/kg, compounds 6a₁ and 7a₁ exhibited moderate hypoglycemic activity. The antibacterial and antifungal activity of the title compounds were assayed using agar cup-plate method^{12,13} by measuring the zone

- $\text{R} = 2\text{-OCOCH}_3$: 4a, 5a₁-d₁, 6a₁-d₁, 7a₁
 2-Cl : 4b, 5a₂-d₂, 6a₂-d₂, 7a₂
 4-Cl : 4c, 5a₃-d₃, 6a₃-d₃, 7a₃
 2-Br : 4d, 5a₄-d₄, 6a₄-d₄, 7a₄
 4-Br : 4e, 5a₅-d₅, 6a₅-d₅, 7a₅₋₇
 2-NO₂ : 4f, 5a₆-d₆, 6a₆-d₆, 7a₈
 4-OH : 4g, 5a₇-d₇, 6a₇-d₇, 7a₉
 $\text{Ar} = 2\text{-OHC}_6\text{H}_4$: 5a₁₋₇, 6a₁₋₇, 7a_{4,5}
 4-OCH₃C₆H₄ : 5b₁₋₇, 6b₁₋₇, 7a_{2,7,8}
 C₆H₅ : 5c₁₋₇, 6c₁₋₇, 7a_{1,3,6,9}
 2-Furyl : 5d₁₋₇, 6d₁₋₇

Scheme 1

of inhibition in mm. It can be concluded from Table 2 that among the tested compounds **6b₁**, **6c₁**, **7a₁** and **7a₂** were highly active against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* while compound **6a₁** and **7a₁**, were found to be moderately active against *C. albicans*. However, all the compounds were less active in comparison to ampicillin trihydrate and cotrimoxazole, which were taken as standard drug for antibacterial and antifungal activity study and the results are given in Table 2. The anthelmintic activity was evaluated on adult Indian earth worm¹⁵ *Perituma posthuma* due to its anatomical and physiological resemblance with the intestinal round worm of human beings¹⁶⁻¹⁸, by using the method of Mathew *et al.*¹⁹. Compounds were tested at 50 mg/ml and 100 mg/ml concentration and compounds were kept in 1% gum acacia in normal saline. Compounds **6a₁** and **7a₁** showed moderate activity in comparison with piperazine citrate (50 mg/ml). Result is presented in Table 3.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. IR spectra (cm⁻¹) were recorded on Jasco FT/IR 5300 spectrophotometer in KBr pellets. ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) spectra were recorded on Bruker DPX-300 MHz spectrophotometer using TMS as an internal standard (chemical shift in δ ppm). C, H and N analysis were carried out on Euro EA (Italy) analyzer. Mass spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer Hitachi RMU-6L MS 30 instrument. The physical and analytical data of the compounds are given in Table 1.

3-Phthalimidoethyl substituted benzoic acids (2a) :

To the solution of 2-acetyloxy benzoic acid (7.20 g, 0.04 mol) in ethanol (100 ml), a solution of compound **1** (0.04 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) and 5 drops of glacial acetic acid were added with constant stirring and the mixture was refluxed for about 4 h on a water bath. After cooling

Table 1. Physical and analytical data of the compounds synthesized

Compd.	R	Ar	Mol. formula	M.p. (°C)
4a	2-OCOCH ₃	-	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₆	126
4b	2-Cl	-	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₄ Cl	131
4c	4-Cl	-	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₄ Cl	136
4d	2-Br	-	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₄ Br	121
4e	4-Br	-	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₄ Br	139
4f	2-NO ₂	-	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₆	135
4g	4-OH	-	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₅	127
5a ₁	2-OCOCH ₃	2-C ₆ H ₄ OH	C ₃₄ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₇	154
5a ₂	2-Cl	2-C ₆ H ₄ OH	C ₃₂ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₅ Cl	158
5a ₃	4-Cl	2-C ₆ H ₄ OH	C ₃₂ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₅ Cl	161
5a ₄	2-Br	2-C ₆ H ₄ OH	C ₃₂ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₅ Br	168
5a ₅	4-Br	2-C ₆ H ₄ OH	C ₃₂ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₅ Br	161
5a ₆	2-NO ₂	2-C ₆ H ₄ OH	C ₃₂ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₇	168
5a ₇	4-OH	2-C ₆ H ₄ OH	C ₃₂ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₆	159
5b ₁	2-OCO	4-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	C ₃₅ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₇	161
5b ₂	2-Cl	4-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	C ₃₃ H ₂₅ N ₂ O ₅ Cl	157
5b ₃	4-Cl	4-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	C ₃₃ H ₂₅ N ₂ O ₅ Cl	165
5b ₄	2-Br	4-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	C ₃₃ H ₂₅ N ₂ O ₅ Br	176
5b ₅	4-Br	4-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	C ₃₃ H ₂₅ N ₂ O ₅ Br	166
5b ₆	2-NO ₂	4-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	C ₃₃ H ₂₅ N ₃ O ₇	157
5b ₇	4-OH	4-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	C ₃₃ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₆	155
5c ₁	2-OCO	-C ₆ H ₅	C ₃₄ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₆	161
5c ₂	2-Cl	-C ₆ H ₅	C ₃₂ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₄ Cl	162
5c ₃	4-Cl	-C ₆ H ₅	C ₃₂ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₄ Cl	162
5c ₄	2-Br	-C ₆ H ₅	C ₃₂ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₄ Br	165

Table-1 (contd.)

5c ₅	4-Br	-C ₆ H ₅	C ₃₂ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₄ Br	162
5c ₆	2-NO ₂	-C ₆ H ₅	C ₃₂ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₆	153
5c ₇	4-OH	-C ₆ H ₅	C ₃₂ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₅	154
5d ₁	2-OCO	2-Furyl	C ₃₂ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₇	167
5d ₂	2-Cl	2-Furyl	C ₃₀ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₅ Cl	166
5d ₃	4-Cl	2-Furyl	C ₃₀ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₅ Cl	168
5d ₄	2-Br	2-Furyl	C ₃₀ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₅ Br	167
5d ₅	4-Br	2-Furyl	C ₃₀ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₅ Br	163
5d ₆	2-NO ₂	2-Furyl	C ₃₀ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₇	154
5d ₇	4-OH	2-Furyl	C ₃₀ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₆	158
6a ₁	2-OCOCH ₃	2-C ₆ H ₄ OH	C ₃₄ H ₂₇ N ₃ O ₇	195
6a ₂	2-Cl	2-C ₆ H ₄ OH	C ₃₂ H ₂₄ N ₃ O ₅ Cl	196
6a ₃	4-Cl	2-C ₆ H ₄ OH	C ₃₂ H ₂₄ N ₃ O ₅ Cl	204
6a ₄	2-Br	2-C ₆ H ₄ OH	C ₃₂ H ₂₄ N ₃ O ₅ Br	205
6a ₅	4-Br	2-C ₆ H ₄ OH	C ₃₂ H ₂₄ N ₃ O ₅ Br	206
6a ₆	2-NO ₂	2-C ₆ H ₄ OH	C ₃₂ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₇	209
6a ₇	4-OH	2-C ₆ H ₄ OH	C ₃₂ H ₂₅ N ₃ O ₆	195
6b ₁	2-OCO	4-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	C ₃₅ H ₂₉ N ₃ O ₇	193
6b ₂	2-Cl	4-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	C ₃₃ H ₂₆ N ₃ O ₅ Cl	202
6b ₃	4-Cl	4-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	C ₃₃ H ₂₆ N ₃ O ₅ Cl	205
6b ₄	2-Br	4-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	C ₃₃ H ₂₆ N ₃ O ₅ Br	204
6b ₅	4-Br	4-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	C ₃₃ H ₂₆ N ₃ O ₅ Br	205
6b ₆	2-NO ₂	4-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	C ₃₃ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₇	207
6b ₇	4-OH	4-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	C ₃₃ H ₂₇ N ₃ O ₆	201
6c ₁	2-OCO	-C ₆ H ₅	C ₃₄ H ₂₇ N ₃ O ₆	195
6c ₂	2-Cl	-C ₆ H ₅	C ₃₂ H ₂₄ N ₃ O ₄ Cl	198
6c ₃	4-Cl	-C ₆ H ₅	C ₃₂ H ₂₄ N ₃ O ₄ Cl	217
6c ₄	2-Br	-C ₆ H ₅	C ₃₂ H ₂₄ N ₃ O ₄ Br	209
6c ₅	4-Br	-C ₆ H ₅	C ₃₂ H ₂₄ N ₃ O ₄ Br	214
6c ₆	2-NO ₂	-C ₆ H ₅	C ₃₂ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₆	224
6c ₇	4-OH	-C ₆ H ₅	C ₃₂ H ₂₅ N ₃ O ₅	224
6d ₁	2-OCOCH ₃	2-Furyl	C ₃₂ H ₂₅ N ₃ O ₇	186
6d ₂	2-Cl	2-Furyl	C ₃₀ H ₂₂ N ₃ O ₅ Cl	199
6d ₃	4-Cl	2-Furyl	C ₃₀ H ₂₂ N ₃ O ₅ Cl	203
6d ₄	2-Br	2-Furyl	C ₃₀ H ₂₂ N ₃ O ₅ Br	209
6d ₅	4-Br	2-Furyl	C ₃₀ H ₂₂ N ₃ O ₅ Br	217
6d ₆	2-NO ₂	2-Furyl	C ₃₀ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₇	222
6d ₇	4-OH	2-Furyl	C ₃₀ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₆	216
7a ₁	2-OCO	2-C ₆ H ₄ OH	C ₃₄ H ₂₈ N ₄ O ₆	207
7a ₂	2-Cl	4-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	C ₃₃ H ₂₇ N ₄ O ₄ Cl	209
7a ₃	4-Cl	-C ₆ H ₅	C ₃₂ H ₂₅ N ₄ O ₃ Cl	224
7a ₄	2-Br	2-C ₆ H ₄ OH	C ₃₂ H ₂₅ N ₄ O ₄ Br	223
7a ₅	4-Br	2-C ₆ H ₄ OH	C ₃₂ H ₂₅ N ₄ O ₄ Br	206
7a ₆	4-Br	-C ₆ H ₅	C ₃₂ H ₂₅ N ₄ O ₃ Br	213
7a ₇	4-Br	4-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	C ₃₂ H ₂₇ N ₄ O ₄ Br	209
7a ₈	2-NO ₂	4-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	C ₃₂ H ₂₇ N ₅ O ₆	206
7a ₉	4-OH	-C ₆ H ₅	C ₃₂ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₄	205

Table 2. Antimicrobial activities of some of the compounds synthesized

Compd.	Inhibition zone diameter (mm) ^a		
	<i>E.c.</i>	<i>S.a.</i>	<i>C.a.</i>
6a ₁	18	16	16
6b ₁	21	20	12
6c ₁	21	18	12
6d ₁	17	15	14
7a ₁	18	19	14
7a ₂	18	20	15
7a ₃	16	16	10
DMSO	0	0	0
Ampicillin trihydrate	29	28	12
Cotrimoxazole	-	-	42

^aAverage of three readings.*S.a.* : *Staphylococcus aureus*; *E.c.* : *Escherichia coli*, *C.a.* : *Candida albicans*.**Table 3.** Anthelmintic activity of the compounds synthesized

Group	Compd.	Conc. (mg/ml)	Time taken for paralysis ^a (min)	Time taken for death ^a (min)
1	6a ₁	50	16	28
2	7a ₁	50	14	29
3	6a ₁	100	9	21
4	7a ₁	100	12	18
5	Solvent control	-	-	-
6	Piperazine citrate	15	27	36

^aAverage of six readings.

the resulting solid was filtered, dried and recrystallized from acetone, 2a : yield 70%, m.p. 122 °C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3045 (C-H), 1779 (C=O, acyclic, OCOCH₃), 1767 (C=O, cyclic amide), 1697 (C=O, COOH), 1606 (C=C) and 1428 (C-N); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 2.1 (3H, s, -COCH₃), 4.2 (2H, t, CH₂), 4.3 (2H, t, CH₂), 7-8.1 (7H, m, ArH), 12.2 (1H, s, COOH); MS (*m/z*) : 353.2 (M⁺) (Found : C, 64.51; H, 4.18; N, 3.89. Calcd. for C₁₉H₁₅NO₆ : C, 64.58; H, 4.24; N, 3.96%).

Compounds 2b-g were prepared similarly.

3-Phthalimidoethyl substituted benzoyl chlorides (3a) :

A mixture of compound 2a (0.04 mol) and thionyl chloride (6 ml) in dry benzene was refluxed under anhydrous condition for about 2.5 h on a water bath. Solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the solid thus obtained was recrystallized from acetone 3a : yield 78%, m.p. 128 °C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3025 (C-H), 1779 (C=O,

acyclic, OCOCH₃), 1768 (C=O, cyclic amide), 1698 (C=O, COCl), 1606 (C=C) and 1428 (C-N); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 2.0 (3H, s, -COCH₃), 4.1 (2H, t, CH₂), 4.3 (2H, t, CH₂), 7.1-8.3 (7H, m, ArH); MS (*m/z*) : 371.65 (M⁺) (Found : C, 61.33; H, 3.72; N, 3.72. Calcd. for C₁₉H₁₄NO₅Cl : C, 61.37; H, 3.76; N, 3.76%).

Compounds 3b-g were prepared similarly.

3-Phthalimidoethyl-4-acetyl substituted benzanilides (4a) :

A mixture of compound 3a (0.02 mol), 4-aminoacetophenone (2.70 g, 0.02 mol) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (2.2 g) in carbon tetrachloride (100 ml) was refluxed on a water bath under anhydrous condition for 4 h. The reaction mixture was cooled, filtered and the filtrate was concentrated and the resulting solid thus obtained was filtered, dried and recrystallized from ethanol; 4a : yield 80%, m.p. 134 °C ; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3335 (N-H), 3027 (C-H), 1777 (C=O, acyclic, OCOCH₃), 1768 (C=O, cyclic amide), 1698 (C=O, CONH), 1593 (C=C), 1429 (C-N); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 2.12 (3H, s, -COCH₃), 3.2 (3H, s, OCOCH₃), 4.2 (2H, t, CH₂), 4.4 (2H, t, CH₂), 5.7 (1H, s, NH), 7.1-8.2 (11H, m, ArH); MS (*m/z*) : 470.46 (M⁺) (Found : C, 68.89; H, 4.60; N, 5.71. Calcd. for C₂₇H₂₂N₂O₆ : C, 68.93; H, 4.68; N, 5.95%).

Compounds 4b-g were prepared similarly.

3-(Phthalimidoethyl)-4-substituted cinnamoyl substituted benzanilides (5a₁) :

To a solution of appropriate 3-phthalimidoethyl-4-acetyl substituted benzanilides 4a (0.01 mol) in absolute ethanol (50 ml), a solution of selected arylaldehydes (0.01 mol) in absolute ethanol (50 ml) was added dropwise with constant stirring followed by triethylamine (2 ml). The reaction mixture was then refluxed for 4 h on a water bath⁸. The solvent was distilled off and the residue was triturated with petroleum ether (60-80 °C) and the product thus obtained was recrystallized from acetone : ethanol (1 : 1); 5a₁ : yield 75%, m.p. 158 °C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 1777 (C=O, acyclic, OCOCH₃), 1766 (C=O, cyclic amide), 1699 (C=O, CONH), 1663 (C=C), 1429 (C-N), 755 (monosubstituted benzene); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 7.8 (1H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, CH), 7.9 (1H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, CH), 2.1 (3H, s, -COCH₃), 4.3 (2H, t, CH₂), 4.4 (2H, t, CH₂), 4.6 (1H, s, OH), 5.8 (1H, s, NH), 6.6-8.6 (15H, m, ArH); MS (*m/z*) : 574.46 (M⁺) (Found : C, 71.03; H, 4.51; N, 4.83. Calcd. for C₃₄H₂₆N₂O₇ : C, 71.08; H, 4.52; N, 4.87%).

Compounds 5a₂-d₇ were prepared similarly.

3-(Phthalimidoethyl)-4-(5-substituted isoxazoline) substituted benzanilides (6a₁) :

To a mixture of compounds 5a₁-d₇ (0.01 mol) and hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.695 g, 0.01 mol) in ethanol (50 ml), a solution of sodium acetate (1 g) in glacial acetic acid (20 ml) was added and the contents were refluxed for 8 h on a water bath. The reaction mixture was concentrated, cooled and the solid thus separated was filtered, dried and recrystallized from ethanol : acetone (1 : 1); 6a₁ : yield 65%, m.p. 192 °C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3385 (N-H), 2907 (-CH-), 1776 (-C=O, acyclic, OCOCH₃), 1760 (-C=O, cyclic amide), 1698 (C=O, CONH), 1665 (C=C), 1418 (C-N), 737 (monosubstituted benzene); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 1.8 (1H, d, *J* 6.6 Hz, CH), 2.1 (1H, t, *J* 7.1 Hz, CH), 2.3 (3H, s, -COCH₃), 3.4-3.6 (1H, m, CH-Ar), 4.32 (2H, t, CH₂), 4.4 (2H, t, CH₂), 4.6 (1H, s, OH), 5.8 (1H, s, NH), 6.6-8.6 (15H, m, ArH); MS (*m/z*) : 589.25 (M⁺) (Found : C, 69.35; H, 4.60; N, 7.18. Calcd. for C₃₄H₂₇N₃O₇ : C, 69.26; H, 4.58; N, 7.13%).

Compounds 6a₂-d₇ were prepared similarly.

3-(Phthalimidoethyl)-4-(5-substituted pyrazoline) substituted benzanilides (7a₁) :

To a mixture of compounds 5a₁ (0.01 mol) and hydrazine dihydrochloride (1.05 g, 0.01 mol) in ethanol (50 ml), a solution of anhydrous sodium acetate (1 g) in glacial acetic acid (20 ml) was added and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 6 h on a water bath. After completion, the mixture was cooled and the solid thus separated was filtered, washed with water and recrystallized from glacial acetic acid : acetone (1 : 1); 7a₁ : yield 62%, m.p. 198 °C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3365 (N-H), 3307 (C-H), 1776 (-C=O, acyclic, OCOCH₃), 1762 (-C=O, cyclic amide), 1697 (C=O, CONH), 1682 (C=C), 1434 (C-N), 742 (monosubstituted benzene); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 1.78 (1H, d, *J* 6.6 Hz, CH), 2.2 (1H, d, *J* 7.2 Hz, CH), 2.4 (3H, s, -COCH₃), 4.0-4.2 (1H, m, NH-CH-Ar), 4.35 (2H, t, CH₂), 4.6 (2H, t, CH₂), 4.9 (1H, s, OH), 6.2 (1H, brs, NH), 5.8 (1H, s, NHCO), 6.6-8.6 (15H, m, ArH); MS (*m/z*) : 588 (M⁺) (Found : C, 69.52; H, 4.80; N, 9.62. Calcd. for C₃₄H₂₈N₄O₆ : C, 69.38; H, 4.76; N, 9.52%).

Compounds 7a₂-g were prepared similarly.

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